

Data Governance Checklist for Research Projects

The following is a list of questions relating to 14 areas of data governance for research projects. Ask yourself these questions to make sure good data governance is in place for your institution.

Existing Data Governance

- Do you have any existing data-related policies such as a data management policy?
- Does the data governance for your project reflect [that of the related institutions](#)?

Roles and Responsibilities

- Have you identified a data custodian for the data produced?
- Have you identified any other roles related to data management, such as data stewards and lead chief investigators?
- Have you defined the responsibilities that different roles have in the management of the data?

Training

- Is training provided for those who are managing data?

Data Ownership

- Have you identified who owns the data, which could be (but not limited to) the institution, the researcher or a third party?

Data Location

- Have you identified where the data is being stored?
- Does the data need to be stored in Australia?
- Have you identified the requirements that different states and countries impose on the management and/or handling of data?

Data Handling and Curation

- Have you undertaken any sort of data curation prior to sharing or publishing your data?
- Have you identified the benefits that managing your data will bring?

Data Sensitivity, Classification and Ethics

- Does any of the data identified relate to humans or animals?
- Does the data contain any sensitive information that needs to be deidentified?
- Has Indigenous data been collected?
- Have you assigned a data classification level to the data, such as open, sensitive highly sensitive?
- Have you received ethics clearance for the project or the data?
- Are there any ethics-related protocols that need to be put in place?

Data Storage and Retention

- Is the data backed up?
- Are data storage tools or platforms used for keeping the data safe?
- Does the data need to be retained for a period of time before it can be destroyed?
- Do you have any data retention protocols?
- Have you identified any reasons for retaining the data?

Data Access

- Do you know how others will gain access to the data?
- Do you know who can access your data?
- Will a data request form be required?
- Will a [data sharing agreement](#) need to be put in place?
- Are there any constraints for accessing the data or is it openly available?

Licencing, Copyright and IP

- Is there an agreement on the licence that will be applied to the data?
- Are there any copyright or IP considerations that need to be made before the data is shared?

Data Reuse

- Do you identify how the data is likely to be reused?

Tools to Support Data Governance

- Are any tools (e.g. databases, repositories, and internal or external processes) provided to support the management of the data created from the project?

Data Type, Format and Size

- Do you understand the nature and type of data that is being collected and used by the project, given that they will impact the sensitivity, ethics, licensing and handling of the data and access to it?
- Can you identify the discipline to which the data being collected or used is related (e.g. STEM, HASS, Indigenous Studies, Non-Traditional Research Outputs or NTROs)?
- Do you know the size of the data being collected?
- Do you know the format of the data being collected?
- Have data quality and data assurance techniques been applied to the data?
- Does the collected data adhere to any prescribed standards?
- Is the data aligned with any vocabularies?
- Have the [FAIR principles](#) been considered for the management, sharing and governance of the data?
- Have you considered the [CARE principles](#) in relation to the governance of your data?
- Have you considered the [TRUST principles](#) and its impact on how your data is provided in the long term?

Risks

- Have you identified any risks involved with the creation and sharing of your data?
- Has a risk assessment been performed? Have the risks been documented?